

Comparative Studies on the Decarboxylation of Picolinic Acid and Malonic Acid in Catechol

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Kinetic data are reported for the decarboxylation of picolinic acid in catechol. Rate constants and activation parameters were obtained and compared with the results obtained previously for malonic acid in catechol. An interesting parallelism between malonic acid and picolinic acid was observed.

IN the decarboxylation of malonic acid in resorcinol¹ and catechol², the rate determining step appears to be the formation of a transition complex involving coordination between the electrophilic polarized carbonyl carbon atom of the un-ionized malonic acid and an unshared pair of electrons on a nucleophilic atom of the solvent molecule. It appears that the decarboxylation of oxanilic acid³ in catechol involves the same sort of mechanism as does that of malonic acid.

Although picolinic acid, has never been the subject of kinetic study in catechol solvent, the analogy between it and malonic acid suggested that it too should be capable of undergoing decarboxylation by the same mechanism as that of malonic acid² and oxanilic acid³.

Experimental

Reagents :—Picolinic acid used in this investigation was analytical reagent grade, catechol (BDH) analar grade, gray white crystalline solid, m.p. = 105°. The colour of the molten catechol was found to be dark red and was used as solvent without further purification.

Apparatus and technique : The kinetic experiments were conducted in a constant-temperature oil-bath by measuring the volume of CO₂ evolved at constant pressure as described in previous articles^{4,5}.

Procedure : In a reactor about 50g of catechol was taken and an 0.221g sample of picolinic acid in a small movable boat was kept at the end of the movable probe inside the reaction vessel. The set up was then placed in a constant temperature oil-bath $\pm 0.05^\circ$ and when thermal equilibrium was established, the reaction was started simply by dropping the picolinic acid in the molten solvent. The contents of the reaction vessel was agitated for a minute to dissolve the acid in the solvent. The CO₂ gas was collected at room temperature in a measuring burette filled with water which had been previously saturated with CO₂. Several experimental runs were made in each set of experiments and the

deviations are reported along with the rate constants in Table 1.

Results

The decarboxylation of picolinic acid was studied at four different temperatures in catechol. The plot of $\log(V_\infty - V_t)$ vs t was linear throughout nearly the entire experiment indicating that the reaction is of first order where V_∞ is the volume of CO₂ after complete decomposition and V_t is the volume at time t . The average rate constants were calculated from the slopes of the logarithmic plots and are tabulated in Table 1. The thermodynamic parameters were calculated using the Eyring equation based upon the data in Table 1 and are tabulated in Table 2 along with the data of malonic acid previously investigated.

TABLE 1. RATE OF DECOMPOSITION OF PICOLINIC ACID IN CATECHOL

Run temp °C	No. of data pairs	Av. $k_1 \times 10^5$ (sec ⁻¹)	Av. dev.
145	5	1.001	± 0.09
150	4	1.778	± 0.02
160	6	3.311	± 0.04
170	3	10.96	± 0.04

TABLE 2. COMPARISON OF ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE DECARBOXYLATION OF PICOLINIC ACID AND MALONIC ACID IN CATECHOL

Acids	E k cal/ mole	log A sec ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger k cal/ mole	ΔF^\ddagger k cal/ mole	ΔS^\ddagger cal/ mole/deg	$k_1 \cdot 10^5$ sec ⁻¹ at 150°
Picolinic acid	35.4	13.50	34.56	34.34	+2.5	10.96
Malonic acid	32.24	13.33	31.42	31.49	+0.8	110.62

Discussion

The decarboxylation of picolinic acid is kinetically first order. The rate determining step is an intermediate complex between the solute and the solvent similar to that of malonic acid, benzoic acid⁶ and oxanilic acid. The rate constants shown in Table 2 show that the decarboxylation of malonic acid is ten times faster than that of picolinic acid which indicates that in more acidic solvent picolinic

acid decarboxylates more slowly than malonic acid. The picolinic acid forms an activated complex with catechol in a manner analogous to malonic acid, the ΔH^\ddagger of the reaction in a given solvent is expected to be higher than that in the case of malonic acid and this is in agreement with the experimental results. The effective positive charge on the polarized carbonyl carbon atom taking part in the rate determining step is lower in picolinic acid than in malonic acid. In malonic acid the electron withdrawing carbonyl group attached to the α -carbon atom is strong enough whereas in picolinic acid it is weak. The activated complex in the case of malonic acid would be expected to be somewhat bulkier than in the case of picolinic acid. Picolinic acid possesses a higher

entropy of activation than malonic acid. This indicates that the association of dicarboxylic acids with catechol is stronger than with monocarboxylic acids and the association may be in the form via hydrogen bonding.

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